

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Brunel**FIRST NAME:** Benedicte**PROGRAM CODE:** PHD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied USThe author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

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List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Quotes Style
2. Grammar and Syntax (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. Regional Variants (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22-25)
4. Footnotes Formats (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 50)
5. Chicago Fonts Format (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 50-53)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Methods and guidelines to provide high-quality writing according to the academic standards for research papers, dissertations, and Thesis for students. Authors' theories have a purpose students need to methodically go straight to the point to respect their ideas.

2) QUOTES STYLE

Chicago and Turabian styles using Zotero provide a wide to manage quotations, especially block quotations, depending on the circumstances. All these instructions in the given document referred to a specific rule of Turabian style according to the page numbers.

Quote style cannot be up to five (5) lines, and the exceptions on the number of lines refer to the specific style for block quotations. Thus, using citations in the right way will help the student avoid going out of the standard quality required.

The appropriate syntax requirements for block quotations are the use of punctuation and the necessity of a commentary.

Block quotations are not only introduced with punctuation appropriate to the syntax but also followed by commentary.

3) **GRAMMAR AND SYNTAX**

Normally, the Thesis presentation needs to be light for lecture and structured. The language basic is different in UK or the US. Then, writing and editing with the Turabian Style is also based on the general punctuation rules like apostrophes, commas, bullets, ellipses, and quotations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23).

4) **REGIONAL VARIANTS**

American and British English are both part of variants of World English and each has its sociolectic value (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22, 25). Citations aim to relay the thoughts of authors and the quality of their words needs to be presented in an efficient way through references. The spelling and the pronunciation of the word differ but can have the same spelling, for example, Axe — ax; plough — plow; colour — color, centre — center (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25-31).

Therefore, the variation of terminology and stereotyping is also regional and identity specificities. For instance: Soda vs. Soda Pop vs. Pop vs. Coke vs. 'tonic

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5) **FOOTNOTES FORMATS**

There are two types of footnotes: content footnotes, used to format digressive details, and copyright permission footnotes, used to prevent plagiarism. They are indicated by a superscript numeral in the text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 52). For example, footnotes can create a bewildering maze for the reader to unravel (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 52). Therefore, “the use of *op. cit.* and *loc. cit.*, formerly common in scholarly references, is now discouraged” (Turabian 1996, 138).

6) **CHICAGO FONTS FORMAT**

The *Chicago Manual of Style* is focused on book publishing. It refers to the points below (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 50):

1. *Margins*. “The normal page dimensions are 8 1/2 by 11 inches
2. *Fonts*. “The eminently readable Times Roman is perhaps the best choice
3. *Indents*. The standard indent is one-half inch

4. *Paper*. Use only 8 1/2 by 11 inch white paper. A 20 pounds or 24 pounds, high brightness (80+), paper works best
5. *Justification*. "Right margins should be justified (aligned) only if it can be done without leaving large gaps between words
6. *Spacing*. "The text should be double-spaced except for block quotations, notes [and references], captions, and long headings.
7. *Page numbers* for each page beginning a major section of a paper (the first text page, bibliography, notes, appendix) are placed at the bottom center of the page three-quarters of an inch from the page edge

The main headings--the title, the heading for the endnotes, bibliography, or appendix--are presented in full caps, centered, in a bold font, and dropped *two inches* from the top of the page (one inch below the margin) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 52-53).

Block quotations are not only introduced with punctuation appropriate to the syntax but also followed by commentary.

7) **CONCLUSION**

To summarize, writing a quality document requires structure and discipline. The Chicago style which is a way of giving references to the author's sources is useful. However, each institute has written rules for research and dissertations, and the Turabian style is the standard for respecting the reliability of sources.

Then, the obvious goal is to avoid plagiarism and appropriate the writings of other authors. However, even if it is possible to use paraphrase, the ideal is to use footnotes to remain faithful to the author's ideas.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
- Turabian, Kate L. 1996. *A Manual for Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Press.

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